

Learner Engagement in Araling Panlipunan Through Interactive and Contextualized Teaching Strategies Among Grade IV Learners of Julian A. Pastor Memorial Elementary School

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Abstract

Learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan remains a challenge, as many elementary learners struggle to apply, integrate, and relate concepts to real-life situations due to the continued use of traditional teaching approaches. This condition often results in limited participation and shallow understanding of lesson content. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of interactive and contextualized teaching strategies in enhancing learner engagement in terms of application, integration, and relevance among Grade IV learners.

A mixed-method research design was employed involving 50 Grade IV learners purposively selected based on low engagement in Araling Panlipunan. Data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire administered before and after the intervention, as well as focus group discussions to obtain qualitative insights. Quantitative data were analyzed using weighted mean and composite mean, while qualitative data were examined through thematic analysis.

Results revealed that prior to the intervention, learners demonstrated moderate engagement in application (WM = 2.6), integration (WM = 2.5), and relevance (WM = 2.64). After the implementation of game-based, scenario-based, and project-based strategies, learner engagement significantly improved to highly engaged levels. Application increased to weighted means ranging from 3.7 to 3.8, indicating improved ability to explain concepts, provide real-life examples, and perform tasks independently. Integration improved as learners were able to connect prior and new lessons and utilize multiple sources of information, while relevance increased through active participation, meaningful questioning, and stronger connection of lessons to real-life and community experiences. However, challenges such as difficulty in deeper concept integration, limited resources, and varying levels of comprehension were identified.

The study concludes that interactive and contextualized teaching strategies significantly enhance learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan. Sustained implementation of these strategies, supported by appropriate teacher guidance, is recommended to promote meaningful and active learning.

Keywords: *learner engagement, Araling Panlipunan, contextualized teaching, interactive strategies, elementary learners*

Introduction

Araling Panlipunan plays an important role in developing learners' understanding of society, culture, and civic responsibility. However, many learners struggle to engage with the subject due to traditional teaching methods that focus on memorization rather than meaningful understanding. These challenges result in low participation, limited application of concepts, and difficulty in relating lessons to real-life situations. Research suggests that interactive and contextualized teaching strategies can improve learner engagement by making lessons more relevant and connected to students' experiences and communities.

Despite these approaches, classroom observations show that learners still experience difficulty in applying, integrating, and relating concepts in Araling Panlipunan. This highlights the need to examine the effectiveness of strategies such as game-based, scenario-based, and project-based learning in improving engagement.

This study therefore aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of interactive and contextualized teaching strategies in enhancing learner engagement among Grade IV pupils of Julian A. Pastor Memorial Elementary School. It also sought to identify the types of interactive approaches that can enhance the pupils' ability to apply, integrate, and relate concepts to real-life situations.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How may the level of learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan prior to the implementation of interactive and contextualized teaching strategies be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. application;
 - 1.2. integration;
 - 1.3. relevance
2. What interactive and contextualized teaching strategies can be implemented to improve learner engagement in terms of:
 - 2.1. game-based strategies;
 - 2.2. scenario-based strategies; and
 - 2.3. project-based strategies?
3. What is the level of learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan after the implementation of these strategies?
4. What challenges do learners encounter in the implementation of interactive teaching strategies?
5. Based on the results of the study, what activities may be proposed to further enhance learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan?

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-method research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to fully understand learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan. The quantitative data provided measurable results on engagement levels, while qualitative data offered deeper insights into the students' experiences with interactive and contextualized teaching strategies.

.Participants

The participants in this study were 50 Grade IV pupils from different sections of the school, selected for their low engagement in Araling Panlipunan. Ten pupils from each section were purposively chosen, and a researcher-made questionnaire was used to measure their engagement levels before and after the intervention. Additionally, two pupils from each section participated in a focus group discussion (FGD) to provide deeper insights into their experiences and challenges with the interactive and contextualized teaching strategies.

Research Instruments

Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire and focus group discussions. The questionnaire measured learner engagement in terms of application, integration, and relevance using a 4-point Likert scale. The Focused Group Discussion provided deeper insights into learners' experiences and challenges.

Procedure

Permission was secured prior to data collection. A pre-implementation questionnaire was administered to determine baseline engagement. Interactive and contextualized strategies, including game-based, scenario-based, and project-based activities, were then implemented. After the intervention, a post-questionnaire and focus group discussions were conducted.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using weighted mean and composite mean, while qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis. Ethical considerations such as confidentiality and voluntary participation were observed.

Results

Section 1: Level of Engagement of Grade 4 Learners in Araling Panlipunan Before the Implementation of Contextualized and Interactive Teaching Strategies

The results revealed that prior to the implementation of the intervention, learners demonstrated a moderate level of engagement in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 1:
Pre-Implementation Level of Learner Engagement in Terms of Application

Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Using Araling Panlipunan lessons to explain or talk about issues happening in school or in the community.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
2. Giving real-life examples when completing activities or answering questions in Araling Panlipunan.	2.7	Engaged
3. Using what was learned in Araling Panlipunan to accomplish simple tasks or activities required in class.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
4. Using maps, charts, pictures, or timelines in Araling Panlipunan to better understand lessons or events.	2.9	Engaged
5. Applying concepts from Araling Panlipunan to understand or respond to new or current events.	2.8	Engaged
6. Showing understanding of Araling Panlipunan lessons during hands on class activities	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
7. Using learned concepts to complete projects or written outputs in Araling Panlipunan.	2.6	Engaged
8. Demonstrating learned concepts during group work in Araling Panlipunan.	2.6	Engaged
Composite Mean	2.6	Engaged

The pre-implementation results for Application showed a composite mean of **2.6** (Engaged), indicating that learners had a developing but uneven ability to apply Araling Panlipunan concepts. Some indicators, such as using lessons to explain real-life issues and applying knowledge to tasks, received a mean of **2.4**, suggesting that learners struggled with independent application and needed more guidance. However, learners performed better in activities like using visual tools, which had a mean of **2.9**, and applying concepts to current events (**2.8**). These findings highlighted the need for more opportunities to strengthen learners' ability to independently apply lessons and connect them to real-life situations.

Table 2
Pre-Implementation Level of Learner Engagement in Terms of
Integration

Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Connecting lessons from Araling Panlipunan with ideas or topics learned from other school subjects.	2.6	Engaged
2. Relating previous lessons in Araling Panlipunan to new lessons to support better understanding.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
3. Using books, images, news articles, or other sources to complete tasks or activities for Araling Panlipunan.	2.7	Engaged
4. Combining ideas from different lessons during group activities in Araling Panlipunan.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
5. Showing how events in Araling Panlipunan are connected through cause-and-effect relationships.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
6. Using information from other lessons to understand new topics in Araling Panlipunan.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
7. Sharing experiences from home or the community that relate to Araling Panlipunan discussions.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
8. Using information from pictures, videos, or readings to explain ideas in Araling Panlipunan.	2.7	Engaged
Composite Mean	2.5	Engaged

The pre-implementation results for integration showed a composite mean of **2.5** (Engaged), suggesting that learners were somewhat able to connect ideas in Araling Panlipunan but had difficulty with deeper integration tasks. They performed better in connecting lessons to other subjects (2.6) and using resources like books and images (2.7), but struggled with relating previous lessons to new ones (2.4) and understanding cause-and-effect relationships (2.4). These findings highlight the need for more support in helping students link lessons and develop critical thinking skills.

Table 3
Pre-Implementation Level of Learner Engagement in Terms of
Relevance

Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Recognizing the importance of Araling Panlipunan lessons in daily life, family life, or personal experiences.	2.6	Engaged
2. Showing increased interest in Araling Panlipunan when lessons include local places, people, or situations.	2.7	Engaged
3. Participating more in Araling Panlipunan discussions that involve real issues in the community.	2.4	Slightly Disengaged
4. Asking questions related to rights, responsibilities, and decision-making during Araling Panlipunan lessons.	2.8	Engaged
5. Gaining ideas from Araling Panlipunan lessons about how to help at home, in school, or in the community.	2.7	Engaged
6. Using information from other lessons to understand new topics in Araling Panlipunan.	2.5	Slightly Disengaged
7. Sharing experiences from home or the community that relate to Araling Panlipunan discussions.	2.6	Engaged
8. Using information from pictures, videos, or readings to explain ideas in Araling Panlipunan.	2.8	Engaged
Composite Mean	2.64	Engaged

The pre-implementation results for relevance showed a composite mean of **2.64** (Engaged), indicating that learners recognized the importance of Araling Panlipunan but still required further support in applying lessons to real-life situations. They were engaged when lessons involved local contexts (2.7) and showed interest in learning about rights and responsibilities (2.8), but struggled with participation in discussions on community issues (2.4) and connecting ideas from other subjects (2.5). These results suggest the need for more opportunities to engage in discussions and integrate learning across subjects.

Section 2: Interactive and Contextualized Strategies Implemented to Enhance Learner Engagement in Araling Panlipunan

The study revealed moderate engagement in Araling Panlipunan among Grade IV learners, with weaknesses in application, integration, and relevance. This led to the implementation of interactive and contextualized strategies, including game-based, scenario-based, and project-based activities, to enhance learner engagement.

Game-Based Strategies

Game-based strategies helped learners apply environmental concepts through interactive activities like quizzes and competitions. These activities made learning enjoyable and encouraged students to participate confidently in class discussions.

Scenario-Based Strategies

Scenario-based strategies allowed learners to engage in role-playing and community meetings, encouraging them to think critically about environmental issues. This approach fostered a deeper sense of empathy and responsibility toward real-life situations.

Project-Based Strategies

Project-based strategies enabled learners to apply Araling Panlipunan concepts by creating posters, maps, and presentations about local environmental issues. These activities connected lessons to their communities, helping students understand the relevance of sustainable development.

Section 3: Level of Engagement of Grade 4 Learners in Araling Panlipunan After the Implementation of Contextualized and Interactive Teaching Strategies

The results showed significant improvement in learner engagement after implementing interactive strategies. Game-based, scenario-based, and project-based activities helped learners apply concepts more confidently.

Table 4:
Post-Implementation Level of Learner Engagement in Terms of Application

Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Using Araling Panlipunan lessons to explain or talk about issues happening in school or in the community.	3.7	Highly Engaged
2. Giving real-life examples when completing activities or answering questions in Araling Panlipunan.	3.8	Highly Engaged
3. Using what was learned in Araling Panlipunan to accomplish simple tasks or activities required in class.	3.7	Highly Engaged
4. Using maps, charts, pictures, or timelines in Araling Panlipunan to better understand lessons or events.	3.8	Highly Engaged
5. Applying concepts from Araling Panlipunan to understand or respond to new or current events.	3.9	Highly Engaged
6. Showing understanding of Araling Panlipunan lessons during hands on class activities	3.6	Highly Engaged

7. Using learned concepts to complete projects or written outputs in Araling Panlipunan.	3.7	Highly Engaged
8. Demonstrating learned concepts during group work in Araling Panlipunan.	3.8	Highly Engaged
Composite Mean	3.75	Highly Engaged

The post-implementation results for application showed a composite mean of **3.75** (Highly Engaged), indicating that learners applied Araling Panlipunan concepts more confidently. They showed significant improvement in using lessons to explain real-life issues (**3.7**) and providing real-life examples during activities (**3.8**). The highest score of **3.9** was earned for applying concepts to current events, suggesting that students became more engaged with social issues and demonstrated stronger curiosity and responsibility. These improvements highlight the effectiveness of interactive strategies in fostering practical application of knowledge.

Table 5
Post-Implementation Level of Learner Engagement in Terms of Integration

Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Connecting lessons from Araling Panlipunan with ideas or topics learned from other school subjects.	3.8	Highly Engaged
2. Relating previous lessons in Araling Panlipunan to new lessons to support better understanding.	3.7	Highly Engaged
3. Using books, images, news articles, or other sources to complete tasks or activities for Araling Panlipunan.	3.6	Highly Engaged
4. Combining ideas from different lessons during group activities in Araling Panlipunan.	3.8	Highly Engaged
5. Showing how events in Araling Panlipunan are connected through cause-and-effect relationships.	3.9	Highly Engaged
6. Using information from other lessons to understand new topics in Araling Panlipunan.	3.6	Highly Engaged
7. Sharing experiences from home or the community that relate to Araling Panlipunan discussions.	3.7	Highly Engaged
8. Using information from pictures, videos, or readings to explain ideas in Araling Panlipunan.	3.8	Highly Engaged
Composite Mean	3.74	Highly Engaged

For integration, the composite mean was **3.74** (Highly Engaged), reflecting strong improvement in connecting Araling Panlipunan concepts across lessons and real-life situations. Learners excelled in connecting lessons to other subjects (**3.8**) and in using a variety of resources, including books and images (**3.6**). The highest score of **3.9** was achieved in demonstrating cause-and-effect relationships, indicating stronger analytical skills. This suggests that students are now better able to relate and integrate knowledge across subjects and experiences.

Table 6
Post-Implementation Level of Learner Engagement in Terms of Relevance

Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Recognizing the importance of Araling Panlipunan lessons in daily life, family life, or personal experiences.	3.8	Highly Engaged
2. Showing increased interest in Araling Panlipunan when lessons include local places, people, or situations.	3.9	Highly Engaged
3. Participating more in Araling Panlipunan discussions that involve real issues in the community.	3.7	Highly Engaged
4. Asking questions related to rights, responsibilities, and decision-making during Araling Panlipunan lessons.	3.7	Highly Engaged
5. Gaining ideas from Araling Panlipunan lessons about how to help at home, in school, or in the community.	3.8	Highly Engaged
6. Using information from other lessons to understand new topics in Araling Panlipunan.	3.7	Highly Engaged
7. Sharing experiences from home or the community that relate to Araling Panlipunan discussions.	3.8	Highly Engaged
8. Using information from pictures, videos, or readings to explain ideas in Araling Panlipunan.	3.9	Highly Engaged
Composite Mean	3.81	Highly Engaged

Relevance showed a composite mean of **3.81** (Highly Engaged), indicating a significant improvement in learners' ability to connect Araling Panlipunan to their own lives. Students demonstrated a strong understanding of the subject's relevance to daily and family life (**3.8**) and showed increased interest when lessons involved local contexts (**3.9**). They also became more active in discussions about community issues (**3.7**) and gained clearer insights into how they can contribute to their surroundings (**3.8**). These results highlight how contextualized learning activities enhanced the students' appreciation of the subject's real-life application.

Section 4: Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Interactive Teaching Strategies

In this study, the challenges faced by learners during the implementation of interactive and contextualized teaching strategies in Araling Panlipunan were explored. Thematic analysis revealed three main areas of difficulty: intellectual, psychological, and economic factors, which influenced learners' engagement with the strategies.

Theme 1: Intellectual

Thematic Chart A Intellectual Factors

Participants	Responses
A,B,C,D,F,H,J	Had difficulty answering questions during game-based activities
A,C,E,G,I,	Struggled with the fast pace of the games

In thematic Chart A, many students struggled with cognitive demands during game-based activities. As seen in the responses, learners found the fast-paced nature of the games challenging, which affected their ability to recall concepts quickly and accurately. These difficulties highlight the importance of managing cognitive load and providing clearer guidance during interactive learning activities.

Theme 2: Psychological

Thematic Chart B Psychological factors

Participants	Responses
A,C ,D, I,J	Felt frustrated by incorrect answers
A,C,E,G,I,	Experienced pressure when not knowing how to act
B, f, H, J	Felt stressed when unable to finish the project on time

In thematic Chart B, students reported feeling frustrated when giving incorrect answers, experiencing pressure during role-playing activities, and stress from time constraints in project-based tasks. As seen in the responses, these emotional challenges hindered their participation and engagement. Offering reassurance, clear expectations, and creating a supportive learning environment can help reduce these psychological barriers.

Theme 3: Economic

Thematic Chart C Economic Factors

Participants	Responses
A,B,D, E,F,G,I,J	Unavailability of materials to use for projects
C, H	Difficulty in affording the cost of materials needed for project-based activities.

In thematic Chart C, economic factors were a significant challenge for students, with many reporting a lack of materials at home and the inability to afford necessary supplies for projects. As seen in the responses, these economic limitations prevented students from completing their tasks. Teachers could alleviate this by providing low-cost resources or encouraging collaborative work to ensure equal participation for all learners.

Section 5: Proposed Learning Activities

Based on the results of the study, several activities may be recommended to further enhance learner engagement in Araling Panlipunan. The findings showed that learners responded well when the lessons were interactive and connected to their own experiences. They enjoyed activities that allowed them to participate, think, and relate the concepts to situations they were familiar with. These kinds of approaches helped them understand the lessons more deeply and encouraged them to take part with greater confidence.

To support these positive outcomes, the proposed activities were created to build on the areas where students improved and to address the parts of the lesson where they previously showed signs of slight disengagement. The revised intervention now centers on three types of performance tasks, specifically game based, project based, and scenario-based activities. These activities offer meaningful and enjoyable learning experiences where students can apply what they know, connect their past and present lessons, and see the relevance of Araling Panlipunan in real issues within their community.

Overall, these performance tasks aim to promote active participation in the classroom, strengthen the learners ability to relate previous knowledge to new ideas, and help them appreciate the importance of the lessons in their daily lives. Through these activities, the study hopes to deepen the learners understanding and interest in Araling Panlipunan while providing learning experiences that are purposeful, meaningful, and responsive to their needs.

Discussion

The findings revealed that interactive and contextualized teaching strategies had a significant positive impact on learners' engagement in Araling Panlipunan. The improvement from moderate engagement to highly engaged levels in application, integration, and relevance indicated that learners became more active, confident, and capable of connecting classroom lessons to real-life situations. By using game-based, scenario-based, and project-based activities, students were able to engage in activities that encouraged participation, collaboration, and deeper understanding of the subject matter. These strategies helped students not only grasp the concepts but also apply them to real-world problems, enhancing their overall learning experience.

Moreover, the results also highlighted that learners became more engaged when lessons were meaningful and directly connected to their personal experiences. The inclusion of local contexts, real-life issues, and multimedia resources further strengthened their connection to the subject. As learners saw the relevance of Araling Panlipunan in their daily lives, their motivation

and willingness to participate in class activities grew. However, some challenges emerged during the implementation of these strategies, including the lack of resources, difficulty in completing some tasks, and challenges related to collaboration during group activities. These issues underline the importance of having a well-organized plan, clear instructions, and consistent teacher support to ensure that all students can fully benefit from these interactive strategies.

In conclusion, these findings suggest that interactive and contextualized strategies foster meaningful, active, and relevant learning experiences among Grade IV learners in Araling Panlipunan. While the intervention successfully enhanced student engagement, it also emphasized the need for further support in areas such as resource availability and task management. By addressing these challenges through careful planning, clear communication, and ongoing teacher guidance, educators can ensure that these strategies remain effective in creating an engaging and inclusive learning environment. Ultimately, this approach not only strengthens students' understanding but also helps them become more reflective, critical, and engaged learners.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions were drawn. First, learners initially exhibited only a moderate level of engagement in application, integration, and relevance, highlighting the need for more meaningful and interactive teaching approaches in Araling Panlipunan. Second, interactive and contextualized strategies, including game-based, scenario-based, and project-based activities, were found to be effective in increasing learner participation and interest during class activities. Third, learners demonstrated significant improvements in their engagement levels after the implementation of these strategies, showing increased confidence, better participation, and a deeper understanding of the lessons. However, students also faced intellectual, psychological, and economic challenges, such as difficulty keeping up with fast-paced activities, feeling pressure during performances, and lacking materials for projects. Finally, the proposed learning activities can further enhance engagement by helping students apply, integrate, and relate Araling Panlipunan lessons to real-life situations.

Recommendations

Based on these conclusions, the following recommendations are offered. Interactive and contextualized strategies should be used in other Araling Panlipunan topics and grade levels to sustain student interest and improve understanding across various lessons. Teachers may benefit from training or workshops to enhance their skills in effectively designing and implementing these strategies in the classroom. Additionally, the use of game-based, scenario-based, and project-based activities should continue in future quarters to maintain high levels of engagement. To ensure broader participation, further learning activities can be provided to cover additional competencies and give students varied opportunities to perform. Lastly, future studies with a larger scope should be conducted to validate the effectiveness of these strategies and explore their long-term impact on student learning.

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